

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART X.

BY PARESH CHANDRA DUTTA AND RAMANI MOHAN SINHA.

Indigoid dyes derived from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2:3'-dione have been described.

9-Phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 471) has been condensed with thioindoxyl and with isomeric benzthioindoxyls such as 6:7, 4:5 and 5:6 with a view to studying the influence of the position of additional benzene ring in the thionaphthene nucleus on the colour of these indigoid dyes. The parent substance, the condensation product of the dione with thioindoxyl, is a violet dye and the condensation products with 6:7- and 4:5-benzthioindoxyls are chocolate dyes and the product with 5:6-compound, a bluish violet dye. This is in conformity with the findings of one of the present authors (Dutta, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 1319; 1935, 68, 1447; 1936, 69, 2343) that, if an additional benzene ring is introduced in the thionaphthene nucleus to load the molecule, the most favourable position for the deepening effect on colour is the 5:6-position; on the other hand 4:5 and 6:7-positions have a lightening effect.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

3':9-Phenanthrathiophene-2-thionaphthene-indigo.

9-Phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.66 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (50 c.c.) and 0.35 g. hydroxythionaphthene in 10 c.c. acetic acid. Into the separate solutions a current of carbon dioxide was passed for sometime and then the solutions were mixed together. The mixed solution was refluxed in a current of carbon dioxide with the addition of 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid when it became dark brown and a reddish violet crystalline mass separated out. It was filtered, the precipitate collected and washed with acetic acid and water. It was then recrystallised from pyridine in violet slender needles, melting above 290°. The dye dissolves in an alkaline hydrosulphite vat with a yellow colour and dyes cotton a violet shade. (Found: C, 72.56; H, 3.21. $C_{24}H_{12}O_2S_2$ requires C, 72.72; H, 3.03 per cent).

3' : 9-Phenanthrathiophene-2-(6:7)-benzthionaphthene-indigo

was prepared like the previous compound from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.66 g.) and 6:7-benzthioindoxyl (0.5 g.). It was recrystallised from nitrobenzene in small chocolate needles, melting above 295°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a brownish violet colour and in alkaline hydrosulphite with a yellowish brown colour from which it dyes cotton a dark chocolate shade. (Found : C, 74.98 ; H, 3.21. $C_{21}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires C, 75.33 ; H, 3.14 per cent).

3' : 9-Phenanthrathiophene-2-(4:5)-benzthionaphthene-indigo

was prepared in a way similar to the previous compounds from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.66 g.) and 4:5-benzthioindoxyl (0.5 g.). It was obtained as a chocolate crystalline mass from nitrobenzene, m. p. above 295°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a blue colour and dyes cotton from an orange-yellow hydrosulphite vat a chocolate shade. (Found : C, 75.14 ; H, 3.19 per cent).

3' : 9-Phenanthrathiophene-2-(5:6)-benzthionaphthene-indigo

was prepared similarly from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione and 5:6-benzthioindoxyl. It was recrystallised from nitrobenzene in violet needles, melting above 295°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a blue colour and dyes cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat a blue shade. (Found : C, 75.21 ; H, 3.16 per cent).